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**VERNACULAR CONTENT: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MICROTOPYNOMS
IN ASTANA AND LONDON**

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Abstract. *This study explores the conceptual, linguistic, and cultural parameters of microtoponyms to understand the historical, cultural, mental, and linguistic characteristics of national languages, facilitating their active development and dissemination. This research contributes to defining mental boundaries among different nations and highlights the uniqueness of national vernacular content. The aim is to investigate the key features of naming microtoponymic objects in Kazakh and English vernacular contexts. Methods employed include lexico-semantic analysis, comparative analysis, linguistic and cultural analysis, and analytical-synthetic methods. The study emphasizes the significance of microtoponyms in understanding cultural and linguistic traits and their role in shaping national identities. Analysis of microtoponyms in Astana and London revealed motives related to professional activities, urban areas, geographical locations, and cultural references. Kazakh microtoponyms often feature national symbols, while English names predominantly reflect national allusions. The conclusion emphasizes the need for further research on microtoponyms to deepen understanding of cultural and linguistic aspects of national identities.*

Keywords: *vernacular content, linguistics, cognitive and communicative mechanisms, geographical objects, historical and cultural context.*

The term "vernacular" is usually used to refer to something that is characteristic of a particular locality or social group. In the context of vernacular linguistics, it can refer to linguistic phenomena, cultural features, or the names of local objects that are used in the daily lives of people in a given region, but are not necessarily official or widespread. Thus, vernacular elements reflect the unique features of the local culture and the local language.

The connotation of the term "vernacular" in this context means local, folk, belonging to a particular community or locality. In this case, vernacular names reflect the unique features of local culture, their use may be limited to certain communities or local residents, while they may not be widespread or officially recognized.

Vernacular linguistics usually focuses on the study of local linguistic phenomena, dialects, and the use of local names and expressions, which includes an analysis of vocabulary, grammar, and phonetics, as well as cultural aspects related to these linguistic elements.

The comparison of the microtoponyms of the Kazakh and English languages of the capital names of Astana and London is due to the need to establish similar and different features in the naming culture and building spatial relationships between urban objects. Establishing all possible connections between linguistic and cognitive-communicative tools is relevant from the point of view of understanding the interaction between semantic components and the historical and cultural context behind them.

The toponymic vocabulary of the Kazakh and English languages was considered in the work of A. K. Meirbekov [1] from the point of view of cognitive processes and structures. Based on the clarification of the etymology of the anthroponyms of a certain region, an idea of the image of the world was formed. In this paper, a general description of Kazakh and English toponyms was given without analyzing specific localities.

Research by A. Zhussupov [2] focuses on the formation of a toponymic map of Kazakhstan with the representation of toponyms of different linguistic groups and building the toponymic landscape of Kazakhstan, taking into account ethnographic, sociological, and cultural data. In the context of toponymic mapping, the study of hydronyms, cosmonyms, urbanonyms, and microtoponyms is envisaged, but the main focus is on the ethnographic aspect rather than the linguistic one.

The study of the historical features and linguistic possibilities of the national language was considered in the work of M. Sh. Narzilloyeva [3]. The study is aimed at analyzing morphological and syntactic phenomena used in naming geographical objects in Uzbekistan, but insufficient attention has been paid to linguistic and communicative-pragmatic aspects.

A linguistic study of the toponyms of the city of Almaty based on electronic maps is presented in the work of S. Serikova [4]. Based on the analysis of semantic and cultural components in this work, attention was drawn to the ways in which the toponymic fund was enriched. In particular, symbolization, associativity, stylization and imagery were considered, but not enough attention was paid to the informal names of microtoponyms.

When studying Kazakh and English toponymic systems, folk etymology was taken into account, in particular, legends, myths, images-symbols associated with the considered spatial objects. The process of etymological reinterpretation, which involves a cognitive process by which "weak" lexical models are replaced by "stronger" ones already familiar to native speakers, was considered in the study by J. B. Walkowiak, but the Kazakh toponymic system was not analyzed in the work[5].

Microtoponymy studies the names of small geographical features: tracts, pastures, hayfields, wells, rapids, which are mostly known only to local residents. Vernacular content represents the local (folk) names of certain territories or objects, the image of which has been formed in the minds of its inhabitants. In cities, microtoponyms can include unofficial names of microdistricts, microdistricts, structures (government buildings, airports, sports complexes, shopping malls, business centers), and water bodies (rivers, rapids, and pools). One of the most mobile and rapidly changing toponymic strata today is urbanonymy in the capital: Kazakhstan's experience shows how fast the streets of Astana are being renamed and how historical names are being restored.

The results were obtained by analyzing the vernacular names of Astana microdistricts and their associations with various characteristics of the territories, their historical contexts, as well as communicative and pragmatic features. For this purpose, linguistic, historical and cultural aspects of the formation of these names were studied, including literature analysis, interviews with local residents, archival sources and other available sources of information. When studying vernacular names of In Astana, it was found out that, as a rule, collective mental boundaries do not coincide with administratively recognized ones. The onomastics of informal microdistricts are significantly influenced by the names of factories, retail outlets, sports complexes, natural objects (such as rivers), and local communities. Thus, among the microtoponyms representing the names of informal microdistricts of Astana, according to the linguistic principle, several groups can be distinguished.

The first group consists of names based on the names of objects related to the nature of work and employment of people: Myasocombinat, Lesozavod, Kirpishnyi, Agrogorodok, Gazoapparatura, Chugunka. The second group includes names representing other urban objects: Vokzal, Eurasia, Vstrecha (from the name of shopping and entertainment centers), 13 Magistral, Zhagalau-3 (from the name of residential complexes). The third group is represented by names identifying water bodies (Pravyi bereg, Levyi bereg, Yesilsky) or the geographical location of microdistricts (Uygo-vostok). This group also includes names that have preserved the phonetic nature of the Kazakh language: Zhagalau (designation of the river coast, indicating the location of the microdistrict in proximity to the Yesil River), Samal (designation of a light wind, breeze, indicating the location on the Yesil river). Another group of vernacular microdistricts consists of historical names of microdistricts (Slobodka, Tselinny, Kapai). Some names are motivated by the names of groups of people according to nationality (Nemeskyi gorodok) or age principle (Molodeshka)[6].

Given the communicative and pragmatic nature of the naming of Astana's microdistricts, a separate group includes names associated with cultural and historical monuments with symbolic onymic motivation. For example, in honor of Kazakhstan's independence, a monument and an observation tower in Astana called Baiterek were erected in the capital, which became a symbol of the country and are very popular among tourists. The very name "Baiterek" is a transliteration from the Kazakh language and means a pyramidal poplar, which in the national consciousness of the Kazakhs acquired the role of a symbolic tree of life. Another name of the microdistrict, which is a reference to European cultural monuments, is the Arc de Triomphe. This building called "Mangilik El" was erected in honor of the 20th anniversary of independence of Kazakhstan by N. Nazarbayev. Some microdistricts of Astana are based on anthroponyms: for example, the name Novaya Seifullina correlates with the surname of the founder of modern Kazakh literature.

It should be noted that the names of vernacular names are represented by two cultural layers: both Kazakh and Russian names. For example, the name of the microdistrict and, accordingly, the residential complex "Koktem" comes from the Kazakh "spring", the name of the microdistrict and the railway station "Dostyk" is translated from Kazakh as "friendship". But the Russian names have also been preserved: Jubilee, Artyom, Chugunka. Informal names remain in memory much longer than administrative ones, so in addition to the new names, the old Soviet ones also function. The final point of the process of studying geographical names is the creation of so-called mental maps.

Thus, the naming process of natural objects is influenced not only by the properties of the object itself, but also by landscape models and cognitive mechanisms. In addition to the names of microdistricts, there are many local names of the following objects in Astana: streets, enterprises, monuments, residential complexes, cafes, parks, bridges, palaces of culture. For example, the unofficial names of the Seruen Bridge, which were given to it by locals, are the Staggering Bridge (due to the shakiness of the surface) or the Astrological Bridge (due to the presence of a weather vane bordered by figures from the Eastern calendar). The informal name of the bridge along the Alash highway, namely the Humpback Bridge, is due to its arched shape, significantly curved upwards.

The name of the Tree of Life fountain in Astana is associated by locals with a Chupa-chups in its shape. The Ministry of Transport and Communications of Kazakhstan received the local name Zazhigalka after the fire occurred, as well as by association with the shape of the structure, and the regional name of the Ministry of Finance is called Dollar, since the building resembles a dollar in shape, and is also associated with finance. The name of the residential complex "Sem bochka" is associated with an architectural ensemble made of 7 buildings in the shape of barrels. Thus, one of the features of vernacular content in Astana is the use of metaphorical transfer in the shape of buildings. In addition to the names already mentioned, there are such things as Carrots (the Astana Tower business center is bright yellow and elongated), Eggs (the dome-shaped building of the Astana State Archive), Buckets (the Altyn-Orda business center in the form of two twin cone-shaped buildings). It should be noted that the unspoken names of microtoponyms in the city are often associated with historical and cultural symbols of other nations: for example, the Pyramid of the Egyptians (the Palace of Peace and Harmony, symbolizing friendship between different faiths: Christians, Buddhists, Muslims) or the Leaning Tower of Pisa (the 15-storey business complex "Shahnaz").

By analogy with the shape, height, color and other parameters of buildings, such names of structures as Shell or Cabbage (concert hall "Kazakhstan"), Flying saucer (circus building), Lantern (Nazarbayev Center), Syringe (business center "Astanalyk"), Candles (high-rise buildings) appeared, Anthill (the Hilton Garden hotel building), Matrosskaya Tishina (a complex of buildings near Nur Otan), Sistemnik (Parus business center), Karaotkel (the cemetery's name means "black ferry, ford"). A part of Turan Avenue, which is built up with a huge number of high-class restaurants, was named Restaurant Street by locals.

In addition to the parameters of the building, the names of architectural structures can be based on cultural associations: for example, the residents of Astana called the EXPO-2017 balloon the "Death Star", I am guided by the association with "Star Wars", and the name of the Titanic residential

complex has an associative connection with the tragic fate of the sunken passenger ship, since this residential complex surrounded by greenery on all sides. It should also be noted that the linguistic and cultural feature of the microtoponyms of Astana has become the use of several names for the same object. For example, the building of a business center is sometimes called a Book, sometimes a Stack of cash, the Palace of Independence is sometimes a Soap Dish, sometimes a Cake. The Shabyt Palace of Arts also has two names: A Pot, an Ashtray, and the Nazarbayev Center has three: A Lantern, a Spotlight, and the Eye of the Cyclops.

The capital of Great Britain has several names, in particular The Big Smoke (an association with the London smog of the XIX—XX centuries), The city of tears (a metaphor indicating rainy weather in the city). The disparaging name The Great Wen for London was coined by the defender of the countryside, W. Cobbett, who considered the city a tumor on the face of the nation. The following names are also used: Londinium, The Global Village, The City of Dreams, Cockney Town.

Among the unofficial names of London microdistricts, several groups of microtoponyms have become entrenched in the minds of local residents, denoting ethnic enclaves (Chinatown, Little Italy), artisanal microdistricts (Londons Larder, Biscuit town), directly indicating the location of urban facilities (Theatreland is a quarter with about 40 theater venues located near the West End), indicating the geographical location relative to the city (Central, Midtown, Londinium). It should be noted that a large group of unofficial names of London microdistricts are represented by nominations based on the metaphorization of reality: The Square Mile, Bedlam, Devil's Acre, Pedlar's Acre. For example, the name Alsatia has stuck as an association with Alsace, which experienced many years of looting during the Thirty Years' War, since lawlessness took place in this quarter of London, inspiring fear among the local population. The name Devil's Acre was given to the block around St. Ann's Lane by Ch. Dickens [12], and the name Bedlam began to be used by analogy with Bedlam Bethlem Royal Hospital, a hospital for the treatment of mental illness, which was located in this microdistrict.

The names of London structures are also often nominated by association with shape and other characteristics: for example, the Leadenhall Building got the unofficial name The Cheese grater because of the wedge-shaped structure resembling a cheese grater, the commercial building St. Mary Axe in the financial district of London was nicknamed by locals The Gherkin. The tallest building in the UK, London Bridge Tower, is associated by locals with the shard because of its pyramidal shape, which is why it was given the name The Shard. The building, located at 20 Fenchurch Street, was named The Walkie-Talkie because of its shape, which resembles a walkie-talkie tube, the 70 St. Mary Axe building was also named Can of Ham by association with the shape. The London City Hall building is called The Egg, and previously the names The Glass Testicle and The Glass Gonad were also used. The unofficial name Big Ben stands for Westminster (Houses of Parliament), in fact, not all tourists know that Big Ben is actually called the big bell, and not the tower itself.

The city's infrastructure facilities include bridges, churches, parks, and cemeteries. The London Millennium Footbridge has the name Wobbly Bridge, which it received because of its shakiness on the day of its grand opening, after which it had to be closed again for repairs. Several bridges in London have informal names based on the word "Bridge". For example, the Waterloo Bridge is commonly referred to by locals as The Ladies Bridge, because after the liquidation of Peter Lind & Co., 350 women who worked for it lost their workbooks. The Albert Bridge was named the Trembling Lady because of its ability to vibrate. The Old Lady of Threadneedle Street is often used to designate The Bank of England. Chris Church churchyard Cemetery was nicknamed Ithy Park, due to the large number of lice located there. The unofficial name of St. Ghastly Grim Church, St. Olave's church, was given to her by Ch. Dickens and then took root in the popular consciousness. By analogy with the shape of the Lee Valley VeloPark (Olympic Velodrome) was named The Pringle.

In addition to buildings and structures, streets can also be distinguished among the microtoponyms: Street of Shame (to denote Fleet Street, where thousands of reporters and editors working in provincial publications lived), Tin Pen Alley (to denote Denmark Street, where music publishers and other institutions were located), The Silicon Roundabout (to denote Old Street roundabout, the epithet "silicone" is used in association with the world of high technology), Petticoat

Lane (to designate Middlesex Street, which functioned as a fashion and shoe market). The vernacular content in London also includes subway lines: The Charing x Branch was named The Misery Line because of overcrowding and unreliability, and the Waterloo and City line - The Drain because of the appearance of the stations, road sections.: Brentford was named To the Golden Mile due to the high concentration of industry and water bodies: the Thames River is often referred to by locals as Old Father Thames.

Thus, in this study, the microtopomic units of Astana and London were compared. In particular, the following common features of naming geographical objects should be noted: associativity, imagery, metaphor, irony, and the use of symbolic images. Kazakh names were characterized by positive or neutral associations with the names of geographical objects, while in English there was a large number of negatively colored nominations for London itself and its parts. Astana microtoponymy has preserved both Kazakh and Russian names of the Soviet period, while London's is based entirely on national vocabulary, due to the longer history of independent Great Britain. In Kazakh discourse, there are more microtoponyms focused on world themes and allusions (films, literature), while in English discourse microtoponymy is based on national themes. London names are characterized by a high degree of mystification of spatial relations.

When studying the unofficial names of residential districts in Astana, the following groups of nominations were identified: motivated by people's work (Myasocombinat, Agrogorodok, Chugunka), motivated by urban facilities and residential areas (Eurasia - from the name of the shopping and entertainment center, Zhagalau-3 – from the name of the residential area), motivated by the names of water bodies (Right Bank, Left Bank), motivated by the names of the historical plan (Slobodka, Tselinny), motivated by names based on national or age principle (German town, Molodezhka), motivated by names with symbolic content (Bayterek). It should be noted that Kazakh microtoponyms combine two cultural strata: native Kazakh (Baiterek, Dostyk, Koktem) and Russian (Artyom, Chugunka) names.

The names of London microdistricts can be divided into several groups: motivated by the names of ethnic enclaves (Chinatown, Little Italy), motivated by the names of artisanal microdistricts (Londons Larder, Biscuit town), motivated by the names of urban objects (Theatreland), motivated directly by location (Central, Midtown), motivated metaphorically or symbolically (The Square Mile, Bedlam, Devil's Acre, Pedlar's Acre), motivated by historical and cultural allusions (Alsatia, Bedlam).

During the linguistic and cultural analysis of microtoponyms, using the example of the vernacular content of the cities of Astana and London, the main similarities and differences were identified. In particular, among the similar characteristics, such as associativity, imagery, metaphor, irony, and symbolization were indicated. Among the distinctive features, the following were highlighted: the mystical content of the names, many negative connotations, the use of label formulas (addresses) in English, the Kazakh discourse is characterized by bilingual motivation (from Kazakh and Russian words) of microtoponymic units, the use of national symbols and at the same time allusions to world subjects. The main microtoponymic objects in Astana were microdistricts, business centers, residential areas, government buildings, bridges, and in London – microdistricts, business centers, parks, bridges, water bodies, subway lines, streets and road sections.

Priority areas in the future scientific perspective may include the study of linguistic, cultural, cognitive, and communicative-pragmatic parameters of toponymic units, the comparison of different national microtoponymic profiles, as well as official and unofficial names of objects. It is also important to consider vernacular content in terms of word formation, phonetic and grammatical features.

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